

Building and Sustaining a Rare Disease Service

A practical guide to designing,
launching, and sustaining cross-rare
disease services

The Rare Network Innovation Exchange programme
and this how to guide were created in collaboration
with and funded by Alexion, AstraZeneca Rare Disease

Contents

ALEXION
AstraZeneca Rare Disease

THE RARE NETWORK
INNOVATION!
EXCHANGE!

Introduction

When we set up the Alström Syndrome UK and Alström Syndrome service, our aim was to provide support and improve outcomes for people living with Alström Syndrome- an ultra-rare, life-limiting condition with no approved disease-specific treatments. Over time, it has been encouraging to see the service develop into a nationally commissioned, highly specialised model that continues to strengthen and evolve.

Through this process, we have learned a great deal about how to set up rare disease services with the goal of improving patient outcomes quickly and for the long-term, through ensuring service sustainability. We know how challenging it can be to set up and fund effective rare disease services in a complex operating environment, so we wanted to share these insights with others who may be considering how to develop or strengthen services of their own.

This resource is intended for clinical leads, service coordinators, administrators, commissioners, healthcare professionals and patient organisation partners involved in rare disease services. It brings together practical learning on designing, delivering and sustaining services in the NHS, drawing on experience from the NHS England highly specialised Alström Syndrome service.

We believe that five core pillars underpin effective rare disease service delivery:

We hope this guide offers practical, experience-based learning to support the development of effective and sustainable rare disease services.

Professor Timothy Barrett and Kerry Leeson-Beevers

The NHS England highly specialised Alström Syndrome service

The NHS England highly specialised Alström Syndrome service (all ages) aims to support early diagnosis and recognition of complications, prompt intervention using established therapies, close liaison with local medical and allied healthcare teams, offer advice and support for families and education and social care services to maximise development and participation. Care is delivered through family-centred, one-stop multidisciplinary face-to-face and virtual clinics for children and adults, co-delivered by NHS trusts and the patient organisation, Alström Syndrome UK (ASUK).

Professor Timothy Barrett

Timothy Barrett is Leonard Parsons Professor of Paediatrics and Child Health in the Department of Cancer and Genomic Sciences and Director of the Centre of Rare Disease Studies Birmingham. He set up and continues to deliver NHS national specialist commissioned services for the rare diabetes syndromes Wolfram, Alström, and Bardet-Biedl, and a type 2 diabetes service in children.

Professor Barrett established the regional Prader-Willi multi-disciplinary team (MDT) service in 2002; the NHSE highly specialised national MDT service for Alström Syndrome (children and adults, with Professor Hiwot) in 2008; Bardet-Biedl Syndrome (children and adults, with Professor Beales) in 2010; Wolfram Syndrome (children and adults in 2012; Complications of Excess Weight MDT Service West Midlands hub in 2021. He has developed and leads national and international networks for type 2 diabetes in children and rare diabetes. He currently co-leads an NIHR Programme Grant to reduce inequalities in health outcomes for children and young people with type 1 diabetes. He co-leads the LifeArc Centre for Acceleration of Rare Disease Trials and has embedded patient support groups as equal partners within the structure.

Kerry Leeson-Beevers

Kerry is Chief Executive of ASUK a patient-led organisation and has lived experience as her son was diagnosed with Alström Syndrome, an ultra-rare and complex condition. ASUK supports the delivery of the NHS England-funded highly specialised service for Alström Syndrome, delivered in partnership with Birmingham Women's and Children's Hospital and Queen Elizabeth Hospital, Birmingham. Kerry is also the Project Lead for Breaking Down Barriers.

ASUK co-founded Breaking Down Barriers with The Sylvia Adams Charitable Trust, a network of over 70 organisations supporting people living with rare and genetic conditions, with a focus on equity, diversity, and inclusion. Kerry is a co-applicant on NIHR-funded research studies and has contributed to UK, European, and global projects in rare diseases, genomics and drug development. Kerry is experienced in patient and public involvement and engagement and is a patient representative on the England Rare Diseases Framework Delivery Group.

Additional acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge Kay Parkinson (ASUK founder), Dr Richard Paisey (ASUK volunteer) and Professor Tarek Hiwot (ASUK Trustee) for their roles in the establishment and development of ASUK and the Alström Syndrome service.

Declaration of Interest

Professor Timothy Barrett has received consultancy fees from Amylyx and Novo Nordisk as a member of the Paediatric Type 2 Diabetes Global Expert Panel. He has received lecture honoraria from AstraZeneca, Alexion, and Novo Nordisk. He is supported by a UK NIHR Senior Investigator Award.

Kerry Leeson-Beevers has received consultancy fees from Bayer, Roche, Amicus, and Alexion.

Funding

This guide has been developed with sponsorship from Alexion, AstraZeneca Rare Disease. No sponsor had any influence over the clinical recommendations or final content of the guide. All sections underwent independent multi-stakeholder review, including clinicians, commissioners, patient organisations, and data/governance specialists.

Terminology

In this guide, the term “patient” is used to refer to people living with rare conditions. This document is intended as a non-promotional educational resource and does not replace local policies or clinical judgment. Readers should refer to relevant national and local guidelines when making decisions about service design.

Review and updates

This guide will follow a periodic review cycle. Feedback from the rare disease community is encouraged to ensure this resource remains relevant and evidence based.

Chapter 1

Partnership with the Patient Community, Service Providers and Commissioners

Partnerships with the patient community, service providers, and commissioners are foundational to successful rare disease services because they ensure that care models reflect lived experience and serve to address unmet need. Patients and patient organisations can provide insights about daily lived burden, priorities, and outcomes that matter most.

Partnership with the Patient Community, Service Providers and Commissioners			
Involve patient communities from the outset of the service as well as sustained engagement in the long-term	✓	Ensure inclusive engagement with community to balance single dominant voices	✓
Agree service Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) at set-up	✓	Formalise partnerships through contracts and service specification	✓
Plan early for formal commissioning and funding	✓	Select location to optimise access to specialist services and MDTs	✓

Alström Syndrome NHS England highly specialised service case study

The Alström Syndrome service demonstrates how effective partnership – in this case between ASUK and the patient community, service providers, commissioners and funders – can help develop sustainable, high-quality services.

From the outset, ASUK recognised the need for a coordinated specialist service that reflected the realities of living with Alström Syndrome and acknowledged that patient communities are not homogeneous. The service was co-designed with the Alström Syndrome community in direct response to patient and family priorities, rather than applying a standardised model. As a result, patients

and families were willing to travel to a single centre of excellence, as the service could support people who are deafblind, adapt communication to individual needs, and provide practical support such as accommodation and advocacy.

The early stages of establishing a rare disease service are often reliant on goodwill. In the case of the Alström Syndrome service, clinics were initially delivered in non-clinical settings, with healthcare professionals (HCPs) volunteering their time before formal arrangements were in place.¹ One challenge was aligning partners around a shared vision. Commissioners were initially supportive of establishing services but were reluctant to fund

Chapter 1

ASUK's involvement. This reflected a broader commissioning challenge at the time, where the contribution of patient organisations was not routinely recognised as a funded component of service delivery. It was only after ASUK explicitly referenced *The Compact* – a UK Government agreement, developed during David Cameron's premiership, that sets out principles for partnership working between government and civil society organisations in England - that its role as a funded partner was recognised.^{1,2} Additionally, the NHS will only fund a clinical service if it is already established. The Alström Syndrome services were fortunate to have clinics already in place when commissioning was sought, enabling them to meet this requirement and secure NHS funding.

Learnings and recommendations

Measuring service impact and effectiveness:

From the outset, services should agree a clear set of KPIs to assess impact. These may include time from referral to first specialist appointment, the level of coordinated multidisciplinary care, and patient-reported experience and outcome measures. Feedback from patients and staff can also provide valuable insight into whether care is being delivered equitably and effectively.

Considerations for patient partnership:

When working with patient communities, it's vital to ensure inclusive engagement and opportunities for input to balance single dominant voices. At the same time, individuals can play a positive role, with strong patient advocates often effective in holding NHS organisations to account and keeping patient needs visible.

Formalising partnerships for sustainability:

ASUK has a formal contract and service specification with NHS England, clearly defining its role within the service. ASUK staff also hold honorary contracts with NHS trusts, allowing them to attend clinics and work alongside clinical teams. This requires completion of induction, mandatory training, and safeguarding and occupational health checks and access to NHS email accounts.

Service location: When establishing a service, location matters. It is important to consider how patient needs may change over time and whether the service site can facilitate increasing clinical complexity. The adult Alström Syndrome service was initially based in Torbay but was later relocated to Birmingham to provide access to a wider range of specialist services, diagnostics, and transplant facilities as clinical needs evolved.

Clinician support: From a patient support group perspective, identifying clinicians who are motivated to champion the development of a service is critical in the early stages. Engaged clinicians can help translate unmet patient need into a credible service model, align stakeholders around a shared vision, and sustain momentum during periods where formal commissioning and funding are not yet in place.

Chapter 2

Funding Models and Approaches

There are several different approaches for establishing and funding a rare disease service. In the UK, rare disease services can be supported through nationally commissioned clinical services (highly specialised), delegated commissioning through ICBs (specialised) collaborative network models such as rare disease collaborative networks (RDCNs), or through arrangements where NHS services are supported by patient organisations.

Funding Models and Approaches

Identify the most appropriate funding and commissioning route	✓	Build in mechanisms to measure impact, equity, and accessibility	✓
Engage commissioners early and work with clinical leads to develop a robust business case	✓	Plan for funding models to evolve over time	✓

Rare disease collaborative network model

RDCNs are coordination networks that are established and overseen by NHS England, but do not receive dedicated funding to support the running of the network itself.³ Currently, January 2026, there are 28 RDCN services, with clinician time and administrative support absorbed within current provider contracts and job plans, rather than through additional commissioning.³ The role of the network is to bring specialist centres together to share expertise, agree standards, and improve consistency of care, while the responsibility for service delivery and funding remains with individual providers.³

Application requirements and process

To apply to establish an RDCN, applications must be submitted jointly by two or more providers, with one acting as the lead organisation. Applications are reviewed annually by NHS England's Rare Diseases Advisory Group, which advises on which proposals should be supported. As RDCNs sit outside existing commissioned services and contractual arrangements there are no additional funding or formal reporting requirements. NHS England provides light-touch support through the highly specialised commissioning team, including a named commissioning manager and access to an NHS England-approved RDCN logo set-up and running costs must not be reimbursed.³

Dedicated clinic model

A dedicated clinic model delivers care through a formally commissioned specialist service. In England, highly specialised services are commissioned nationally by NHS England for conditions affecting fewer than 400 individuals, while specialised services are generally now commissioned through ICBs.^{4,5} Clinics operate to an agreed service specification and provide coordinated care – diagnosis, treatment, multidisciplinary input, and follow-up – with accountability held by the commissioned provider. Funding is provided through established NHS commissioning routes (e.g., block contracts or nationally agreed arrangements) and supports defined clinical activity rather than network coordination or service development.⁵

Application requirements and process

NHS commissioning is not a grant application; it is a structured process led by commissioners, and services must be established and operational before funding is considered.^{1,4,5} It is essential to determine whether a service is classified as specialised or highly specialised, as this determines commissioning responsibility. Once the appropriate commissioner is identified, services should work with clinical leads to develop a robust business case demonstrating patient need, quality, and value for money, and engage commissioners early to align with commissioning priorities.

Subcontracting to patient organisations model

In a subcontracting model, clinical care is commissioned and delivered by the NHS, while non-clinical care such as care coordination, patient education, peer support, navigation, or registry support

are delivered by a patient organisation. Subcontracting works well for rare disease services because these services depend on highly specialised knowledge, small patient populations, and close relationships with patients and families, all of which patient groups tend to hold.⁶ When services are subcontracted to patient organisations, a formal agreement such as a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) should be in place or a Service Level Agreement. The MOU should consider factors such as review, document management and any training requirements, including which organisation will be responsible or each function.⁷

Stakeholder preferred model

Research on rare disease care models shows stakeholders favour services that are coordinated and practical.⁸ Nationally centralised or hybrid models with national oversight and local delivery are preferable, as they can bring care closer to patients.⁸ Stakeholders also stress collaborative working across organisations, with clear roles spanning administration, care coordination, clinical care and charity-led functions.⁸ Access to relevant records and flexible appointment timing and modes are also key features of effective care models.⁸

Alström Syndrome NHS England highly specialised service case study

ASUK used charitable grants to fund initial service activity to demonstrate unmet need and proof of concept.¹ This pump-priming stage was critical, as NHS commissioners would only consider funding a service that was already operating.¹ Patient organisations should therefore plan for an initial phase of independent funding to establish activity,

Chapter 2

collect evidence, and show value.¹ ASUK moved to a blended approach that combined NHS commissioning and continued charitable and grant funding for clinical delivery for coordination, patient support, and wider family support services.

Currently, ASUK sustains its service through a combination of time limited NHS contracts, which require rebidding at set intervals, alongside additional grant funding to support family services. The organisation measures and reports the impact of its service through six-monthly and annual reports, supported by audits, funding applications, and routine review meetings with commissioners.

ASUK evidenced equity impact through routine reporting on community demographics, analysis of did-not-attend rates, and clear description of how barriers to access were identified and addressed.

Learnings and recommendations

Evolving funding models: Once established, services should plan for funding to adapt over time, with early consideration of governance, data ownership and ethics approval, particularly where charities co-lead delivery.

Demonstrating equity impact: Rare disease services should embed clear measures of equity, showing care is accessible, inclusive and meets the needs of under-represented groups as well as the wider community.

Improving awareness and accessibility: Awareness of highly specialised services and access via referral remain limited. Services should clearly communicate referral routes, funding arrangements and eligibility to improve access and referrer awareness.

Identify commissioning routes and engage early: Services must determine whether they are specialised or highly specialised to identify the correct commissioner, then work with clinical leads to develop a strong business case and engage commissioners early.

Setting up a MOU: Where patient organisations are subcontracted, a formal MOU should define roles, responsibilities, review processes, document management and training requirements.

Chapter 3

Industry Partnerships

Partnerships with industry can play a valuable role in the development and sustainability of rare disease services. They tend to work best when focused on strengthening capability rather than funding core clinical delivery. In rare disease settings, where expertise is often limited and pathways are still evolving, industry support can help build the conditions needed for high-quality care to develop. This might include support for clinician education, multi-disciplinary working, pathway design, service coordination, or activities that improve research readiness.

Industry Partnerships			
Be clear about the purpose and objective of industry partnership	✓	Formalise industry partnerships through contracts to provide clarity around roles and governance	✓
Engage with industry early to enable meaningful patient community input into clinical trial design	✓	Explore opportunities for industry support beyond clinical trials and treatment development	✓

Alström Syndrome NHS England highly specialised service case study

ASUK has invested in building internal capability to engage effectively with industry and regulatory processes. This included engagement with European and international initiatives focused on medicines development and regulation, such as participation in EURORDIS training programmes, representation on the Paediatric Committee at the European Medicines Agency, involvement in the ASTERIX project on innovative trial design, and contribution to the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences working group on patient involvement. This experience

strengthened ASUK’s understanding of the medicine development landscape and positioned the organisation to better engage in subsequent industry-led research collaborations.

While a nationally commissioned highly specialised service for Alström Syndrome is in place, progress in therapeutic development has relied on research partnerships, including collaboration with industry. ASUK has been involved in two clinical trials for Alström Syndrome. Although neither resulted in an effective treatment, both contributed to improved understanding of the condition and informed future research approaches.

Chapter 3

In one partnership, ASUK was engaged at an early stage of product development. Working alongside clinical partners, ASUK supported the company to understand the needs of people living with Alström Syndrome and advised on trial design, accessibility, and inclusivity. Rather than using a contract research organisation, ASUK proposed a model in which it provided logistical and practical support to participants, building on its existing role within the NHS service. This model was contractually agreed and contributed positively to participant recruitment and retention.

In contrast, a second company approached ASUK after the trial protocol had been finalised and recruitment had begun. Due to the complexity and disabilities associated with Alström Syndrome, limitations in trial design made recruitment and retention more challenging. Although ASUK again provided participant support under contract, this experience highlighted the importance of involving patient organisations earlier in the development process to ensure feasibility and accessibility for rare disease populations.

Learnings and recommendations

Engage patient organisations early:

Patient organisations and people with lived experience should be involved as early as possible in the drug development process. Early engagement supports feasible, accessible trial design and improves recruitment and retention in rare disease studies.

Design trials around accessibility, equity and cultural sensitivity:

Clinical trials should proactively assess and address barriers to participation, including disability-related needs, travel and accommodation, visit burden, language and informed consent, socio-economic factors, and cultural or religious considerations (e.g. medication content, timing of visits, and trust in research).

Define roles and formalise involvement:

The role of patient organisations in industry-led research should be clearly defined and proportionate to their capacity. Where organisations contribute to trial delivery or participant support, responsibilities and governance should be formalised through appropriate agreements.

Maintain transparency and trust:

Transparent communication with participants, the wider community, and local healthcare providers is essential. Where industry funding supports patient organisation activities, clear policies and disclosure help maintain independence and trust.

Chapter 4

Transition of Care

Transition planning should be built into rare disease services from the outset, rather than treated as an add-on once patients approach adulthood. Well-designed transition pathways help maintain safety, continuity of care and patient confidence, while reducing the risk of people disengaging from services at critical points.⁹ Although paediatric-to-adult transition is often the focus, services should also recognise that adults with rare diseases experience multiple transitions over their life course and are increasingly living longer.

Transition of Care			
Build transition planning into rare disease services from the outset, recognising transition as a process rather than a single event	✓	Work collaboratively across paediatric and adult teams, using joint planning and handover to maintain continuity of care	✓
Support young people to develop self-advocacy skills, build confidence and independence through individually appropriate, staged support	✓		

Understanding transition as a process, not an event

Transition from paediatric to adult care is widely recognised as one of the most challenging periods for people with rare diseases, as well as for the professionals supporting them. In practice, transition is not a single handover point but a prolonged process that unfolds over several years.¹⁰ During this time, young people may experience changes in clinical responsibility, models of care and expectations around self-management.¹⁰ Without clear planning, these overlapping changes can feel fragmented and overwhelming. Working closely with patient organisations throughout this process can help reduce disengagement, support self-management skills and improve experience for both patients, parent/carers and healthcare teams.

Alström Syndrome NHS England highly specialised service case study

Transition planning is strongly embedded within the Alström Syndrome service. Young people begin their transition journey from around the age of 11 and are supported by a dedicated Transition Coordinator and appropriate resources, including My Life, My Future. Preparation for transition is gradual and structured, with young people attending joint clinics at Birmingham Women’s and Children’s Hospital. Clinical leads and clinical nurse specialists from adult services join paediatric clinics, allowing relationships to develop well before transfer takes place.

Young people are also offered an orientation visit to the adult hospital with the Transition Coordinator.

Chapter 4

This visit helps them become familiar with the adult setting, understand how clinics run, and meet members of the multidisciplinary team in advance. This early exposure helps reduce anxiety and supports continuity at the point of transfer.

Alongside face-to-face support, a range of appropriate digital tools are used to support young people and families through transition. These include the Transition – Knowledge and Skills in Health Care (T-KASH) model, developed by young people from ASUK.¹¹ T-KASH focuses on the knowledge and skills young people may need to manage their healthcare, supports them to understand and cope with change at key life stages such as moving schools or entering the workforce, and helps them consider when and how to disclose their health condition.¹¹ The model also supports young people to plan for their move into adult services in a structured and confidence-building way.¹¹

Learnings and recommendations

Rethink independence and support:

Treat independence as a spectrum, not the absence of support. Agree early on shared expectations across paediatric and adult teams, and tailor support over time to reflect individual communication, decision-making and advocacy needs.

Start preparation early: Begin transition planning in early adolescence. Use individually appropriate discussions, increase young people's involvement in appointments, and support families as roles shift to build skills and confidence gradually.

Plan for same-trust transitions:

If paediatric and adult services sit within the same trust, use shared records and relationships to support handover – but do not rely on proximity alone. Put in place joint planning, shared protocols and protected time for transition activity.

Plan for cross-trust transitions:

When services span different trusts, reduce complexity by agreeing clear pathways, named contacts and documented roles. Invest early in relationship-building to avoid assumptions and gaps in coordination.

Use joint handover clinics strategically:

Acknowledge capacity limits. Where possible, use joint handover clinics to coordinate care, maximise clinical time and support smoother transition, with dedicated coordination and protected time.

Chapter 5

Service Sustainability

Sustainable rare disease services are those that remain responsive to patient needs while demonstrating impact and value. Routine feedback, outcome monitoring, and cost awareness support continuous improvement, strengthen accountability to commissioners, and help services adapt over time.

Service Sustainability	
Keep patient priorities central to sustain engagement and relevance over time	✓
Use routine feedback and service data to demonstrate impact and drive improvement	✓
Use cost-benefit evidence to demonstrate value and support long-term sustainability	✓

Alström Syndrome NHS England highly specialised service case study

The systematic collection and use of patient feedback to support continuous service improvement is a core component of the Alström Syndrome NHS England service specification. ASUK gathers feedback after each clinic using a combination of quantitative measures and open-ended questions, enabling satisfaction and patient experience to be tracked over time. This feedback is shared routinely with clinic leads and service coordinators to inform ongoing service refinement.

Patient feedback and service data are shared with commissioners through annual review meetings and service audits. The feedback consistently demonstrates the perceived benefit of a highly specialised service and its positive impact on health outcomes and quality

of life. In addition to clinic-based care, the service provides coordinated follow-up and practical support that extends beyond clinic attendance, including liaison with local health, education, and social care providers; contributions to assessments and benefits applications; and support to identify grants and funding for essential equipment and activities. Peer-to-peer support, advocacy, education, and social opportunities are embedded within the service model, helping to reduce isolation for individuals and families. This holistic approach is considered to contribute to a reduction in local appointments and fewer unplanned hospital admissions.

A key operational outcome has been sustained engagement with care. Since clinics were established in 2007, the service recorded 100% attendance with zero 'did not attend' appointments up to 2024.

Chapter 5

In 2024–2025, the service recorded its first 'did not attend' when a patient became acutely unwell the day before clinic and was unable to travel. This exceptionally high attendance rate is attributed to proactive coordination, personalised support, and early identification and mitigation of barriers to access.

As of 31 March 2025, the ASUK database included 94 individuals, of whom 43% were children and young people and 57% adults. 61% were born male and 39% born female. 55% of individuals were from ethnic minority communities, and the community collectively spoke 17 different languages. Patients were distributed across England, Scotland, and Wales, with some travelling to Birmingham from as far north as Stirlingshire, and as far south as Truro. ASUK works closely with families to understand specific needs and address practical, cultural, linguistic, and logistical barriers that could otherwise affect clinic attendance.

Learnings and recommendations

Keep patient priorities central: Rare disease services should remain grounded in what matters to people with lived experience and their families. Ongoing involvement of patients helps ensure services remain relevant, responsive, and aligned with real-world needs.

Use feedback and data to demonstrate impact: Routine collection of feedback and service data is essential to demonstrate impact, inform continuous improvement, and support commissioning discussions. Learning from challenges as well as successes strengthens service quality and credibility.

Build relationships and trust over time: Effective rare disease services depend on strong, sustained relationships across

staff teams, patients and families, clinical partners, commissioners, and the wider rare disease community. Dedicated time and consistency are required to build and maintain trust.

Use cost–benefit analysis to support sustainability: Where possible, services should assess the costs and benefits of delivery models, including the wider system impact of coordinated care. Cost–benefit evidence can strengthen the case for commissioning, demonstrate value, and support long-term sustainability.

Example of anonymised feedback form

Post clinic feedback form

Patient feedback

Difficulty attending multiple appointments on the same day

Clinic/Service Coordinator review

Clinic have identified this feedback as a recurring theme across multiple clinics

Agreed action(s)

Review clinic scheduling to better align core multi-disciplinary appointments to reduce travel burden and fatigue for patients and their families

Outcome

Implement changes over a one-month period and monitor impact through subsequent patient feedback

Quick Start Recommendations

Partnership with the Patient Community, Service Providers and Commissioners			
Involve patient communities from the outset of the service as well as sustained engagement in the long-term	✓	Ensure inclusive engagement with community to balance single dominant voices	✓
Agree service Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) at set-up	✓	Formalise partnerships through contracts and service specification	✓
Plan early for formal commissioning and funding	✓	Select location to optimise access to specialist services and MDTs	✓

Funding Model and Approaches			
Identify the most appropriate funding and commissioning route	✓	Build in mechanisms to measure impact, equity, and accessibility	✓
Engage commissioners early and work with clinical leads to develop a robust business case	✓	Plan for funding models to evolve over time	✓

Industry Partnerships			
Be clear about the purpose and objective of industry partnership	✓	Formalise industry partnerships through contracts to provide clarity around roles and governance	✓
Engage with industry early to enable meaningful patient community input into clinical trial design	✓	Explore opportunities for industry support beyond clinical trials and treatment development	✓

Transition of Care			
Build transition planning into rare disease services from the outset, recognising transition as a process rather than a single event	✓	Work collaboratively across paediatric and adult teams, using joint planning and handover to maintain continuity of care	✓
Support young people to develop self-advocacy skills, build confidence and independence through individually appropriate, staged support	✓		

Service Sustainability			
Keep patient priorities central to sustain engagement and relevance over time	✓	Use cost-benefit evidence to demonstrate value and support long-term sustainability	✓
Use routine feedback and service data to demonstrate impact and drive improvement	✓		

References

1. Parkinson, K., 2014. Working with the NHS to develop the Alström multi-disciplinary clinic service. *Expert Opinion on Orphan Drugs*, 2(11), pp.1159-1161.
2. Cabinet Office (2010). The Compact: The Coalition Government and civil society organisations working effectively in partnership for the benefit of communities and citizens in England. UK Government. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/61169/The_20Compact.pdf (Accessed: December 2025).
3. NHS England. Rare disease collaborative networks. Available at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/commissioning/spec-services/highly-spec-services/rare-disease-collaborative-networks/> (Accessed: December 2025).
4. NHS England. Specialised services. Available at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/commissioning/spec-services/> (Accessed: December 2025).
5. NHS England. Highly specialised services. Available at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/commissioning/spec-services/highly-spec-services/> (Accessed: December 2025).
6. Patterson, A.M., O'Boyle, M., VanNoy, G.E. and Dies, K.A., 2023. Emerging roles and opportunities for rare disease patient advocacy groups. *Therapeutic advances in rare disease*, 4, p.26330040231164425.
7. Specialist Pharmacy Service. Patient Group Directions in complex commissioning scenarios. Available at: <https://www.sps.nhs.uk/articles/patient-group-directions-in-complex-commissioning-scenarios/> (Accessed: December 2025).
8. Walton, H., Simpson, A., Ramsay, A.I., Hunter, A., Jones, J., Ng, P.L., Leeson-Beevers, K., Bloom, L., Kai, J., Kokocinska, M. and Sutcliffe, A.G., 2022. Development of models of care coordination for rare conditions: a qualitative study. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases*, 17(1), p.49.
9. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2016) Transition from children's to adults' services for young people using health or social care services (NICE Guideline NG43). Available at: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng43> (Accessed: January 2026).
10. Health Service Executive. Model of care for transition from paediatric to adult healthcare providers in rare diseases. Available at: <https://www.hse.ie/eng/services/list/5/rarediseases/rare-disease-publications/model-of-care-for-transition-from-paediatric-to-adult-healthcare-providers-in-rare-diseases.pdf> (Accessed: January 2026).
11. Breaking Down Barriers. T-KASH transition tools. Available at: <https://breaking-down-barriers.org.uk/t-kash-transition-tools/> (Accessed: January 2026).

